

Portfolio and Risk Management: Growing Investment Portfolio

By Edwin Amuga

Portfolio analysis, risk management

Introduction

Investment in stocks is aimed at taking advantage of eliminating risks and making profits off opportunities in the stock market. It is essential to take into consideration financial accounting when making investment decisions. For this reason, Investors need to have a basic understanding of the critical financial statements of a business and how each project affects the statement. This helps improve communication and cooperation between the financial entities and the investors. This also helps in making better investment decisions.

Stock investment is founded on risk elimination and increasing stock earnings in the face of ever-increasing money velocity. Stock investment is housed as a business on government-supported legal entities. Tax payment is one of the legal requirements that governments demand of businesses which is only made possible when money is earned and profits made. This implies that money-making and risk elimination is the primary goal of any business. The government requires businesses to provide financial insights for the protection of their legal status of businesses. In light of these, businesses adhere to generally accepted accounting principles to meet their tax payment obligations. Investors and the government use the three primary financial statements: the balance sheet, the cash flow statement, and the income statement made from the same accounting data, including the general ledger. Investors pay attention to and use these documents to make their investment decisions. This paper approaches an overview and explanation of investment risk management, portfolio investment, and the importance of financial knowledge and portfolio diversification in a bid to make a fortune in the stock trade.

Many investors are irrational and have biases that cost them significant returns over time. These biases include loss aversion, overconfidence, and bandwagon. Biases must be managed to improve the

performance of investments. These biases allow investors to rely heavily on past returns in their investment decisions. Other risk biases that investors might encounter include non-reporting bias and instant history risk. For the survival of investments, investors need to practically acquire an informed oversight of the market or use financial managers who are informed and trained in investment management.

Market risk exposure can be evaded through solid risk management procedures such as ascertaining, measuring, observing, and administering stock risk, as well as ensuring that the Investor holds sufficient capital against the risk and the risk is sufficiently guaranteed with the occurrence of risks. Risk management is also achieved through diversification. Diversification can be done by allocating assets or selling financial products across stock classes or industries. To reduce high market exposure that might occur due to significant industry changes and competition, including new government regulations, the Investor has to spread their investment across a wide range of stocks in different sectors.

Exhaustively addressing stock volatility risk helps caution the risk if the investors fail to realize the return on investment on other platforms as other stock performances caution them. It also helps capitalize on the Investor's risk-adjusted return rate by maintaining stock risk exposure within acceptable parameters.

Price volatility can be regarded as the dispersion measure around the mean return of a security or a range measure of the price of an asset about the mean level over a specified period. The stock price is volatile when there is a systemic mean variance over time. Less volatile stocks experience little change in prices over a specified period. A good understanding of stock prices determines the possibility of making fortunes in companies investors intend to invest in. The value of accounting information is indicated by the ability of the information in the financial

statements to reflect stock measures. Efficient stocks encourage a country's economic growth and development.

On the other hand, stock markets enhance private capital and facilitate capital market improvement. Dependable and consistent accounting information is crucial for the growth of stock markets since investors rely on adequate information in making informed investment decisions. Accounting information has substantial effects on the volatility of the stock process. In response to this, company managers prepare accounting information to enable potential investors to make economic and investment decisions to lessen the volatility of stocks. Many companies have undergone very turbulent times in the history of their growth, which is related to collapsing investor interests.

Several factors, along with accounting information, such as financial policy, industrial policy, expectations of investors, market supervision, foreign trade policy, and internal factors, can change stock price. Among all the listed factors, accounting information stands out as the most important one used by investors to make investment decisions based on the company stock, as the price of a company's stock reflects the future profit. An investor will only analyze the information contained in the financial statements when evaluating the price of stocks of a company on the bourse only if it furnishes them with helpful information. Due to this, accounting information must possess two qualitative features, relevance, and reliability, for it to be helpful and acceptable to potential investors. If one or none of the qualities are present in an accounting statement and information, it will be considered redundant. One of the most important objectives of financial reporting is providing relevant information to equity investors for estimation of the value of a company.

Trading Risk management

An investor's primary objective is to make a fortune in stock trading. Making a fortune depends on a good understanding of the stock prices of companies in which investors intend to invest. The usefulness of accounting information is indicated by the ability of the information in the financial statements to shed light on stock measures. Efficient stocks spur a country's economic growth and development, and stock markets enhance private capital and improve the capital market. Reliable accounting information is crucial for stock market growth as investors need adequate information to make informed investment decisions. Accounting information strongly impacts the stock price volatility, so managers must adequately prepare and present accounting information to allow potential investors to make economic and investment decisions to reduce stock price volatility. Many companies have undergone very turbulent times in their growth history attributable to crumbling investor interests in companies with volatile stock prices.

It is imperative to address trading risk adequately and caution the risk if the investors fail to meet the demands of a volatile market. Risk management activities are aimed at risk-adjusted return rate maximum capitalization by confining credit risk exposure to tolerable parameters. Other risks include banking book or trading book risk, forex and interbank transactions, swaps, trade financing, equities, commitment extension, swaps, transaction settlements, options, financial futures, bonds, and acceptances. Therefore, it is essential to quantify, examine, and manage credit risk and ensure that the bank holds adequate capital against the risk and is adequately compensated when risks occur. Proposed sound practices include establishing a suitable risk environment, measuring, monitoring, and maintaining adequate stock risk control.

Proper risk management encompasses a methodical and regular review of strategies, obligations, and policies concerning adherence to agreed terms and a systematic understanding of the market; all extensions be done at arm's length basis, and using investors' rating risk system in risk management. The Investor might argue that the exact stock analysis method will depend on various factors. The securities risk management methods must be sufficient for activities and good risk-return discipline used in the risk management process.

Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) and behavioral finance

The Efficient Market Hypothesis posits that prices of stocks are valued efficiently and reflect all the available information at any given time in a liquid market. An investor, like any other market participant, may rationally view the prices of stock based on current and future external and intrinsic factors. This is complemented by observation of how psychological factors influence investors' decisions on stock buying and selling. Therefore, behavioral finance biases influence investment decision-making and must be understood. It is imperative that portfolio managers and investors develop a vested interest in understanding behavioral finance trends and use them to analyze the levels of market prices and fluctuations for decision-making and speculation.

Like any other market, demand and supply forces affect investment, implying that factors affect the buying and selling actions among the participants in the market. Among these are non-economic factors such as behavioral biases, political events such as the infamous Brexit, wars, natural disasters such as earthquakes, currency heading and investments, investor speculation, HFT and Algorithm trading, and business sentiment. These factors have economic significance as they can affect investments in areas that they occur in, either by reducing or increasing investment opportunities and outcomes depending on the type of investment.

Investment requires psychology-based trading strategies offering mental fortitude to stick to strategies and develop traits such as patience and discipline to enable investors to attain consistency in the

market. These strategies help eliminate self-inclinations to seek shortcuts, get distracted or make decisions informed by fear or greed. These traits make investors make irrational and biased decisions despite being informed about market facts and trends.

Behaviors of investors can be logical or reasonable, and biases in them may lead to making bad investment decisions attributed to emotional processes. Mental mistakes and individual personality traits inform investment decisions made by investors. Investment decisions are based on analyzing numbers and performance tables to sell and buy various assets and securities. Investors must use money managers to eliminate these biases that might lead them to make uninformed financial decisions that increase investment risks. These behavioral biases can be of many types, including cognitive and emotional biases leading to irrational decision-making based on attitudes and behavior. Due to these, an investor can be classified as status-quo or overconfident. The best way to eliminate these biases is by making investors aware of them or using investment managers to make informed financial decisions.

Biased investors have very minimal chances of survival since their investment decisions are not entirely based on financial facts and prognosis but on biases that are in no way related to the market condition, new opportunities, and the running of the companies poised to invest in. The CEOs of companies to be invested in are professionals capable of making wise decisions that will affect the performance of companies. Even so, money managers should assess companies' financial performance trends to ensure that investors' monies are on the growth path by avoiding mispricing and correction patterns that CEOs could manage to create an inaccurate impression. Money managers are, therefore, in a position even to make markets efficient since they play oversight roles in the performance of companies and advise their clients against companies that do not perform efficiently.

Elimination of the human element in making financial decisions is essential. It can be achieved by using third-party money management firms or individuals that advise and make informed money management decisions since they have a piece of sizeable real-time information on the state of the market and possess superior market watch and analysis technologies.

Neoclassical corporate finance requires incorporating many factors that affect decision-making on investment. Managers and investors may have beliefs and expectations based on irrational biases that might lead to risky financial decisions. Managers and CEOs of firms and companies may realize this and make market timing moves to take advantage of this. Investors have minimal governance of companies they invest in and can only use such governance tools as the observation of the stock market for declining prices of shares, takeovers, boards of directors, and CEO compensation contracts. Though these tools help in policing a CEO's performance, they are not entirely adequate. Therefore, investors must use money managers to avoid biases in their investment decision-making. Financial advisors or their respective firms arrive at the right financial decisions after evaluating the risks and goals of the Investor and help an investor develop more sophisticated institutional investment strategies.

Money managers are individuals or financial firms that manage the securities portfolio of other individual or institutional investors. Money managers are investment experts and, in most cases, employ people with expertise and experience in research and investment selection options for asset monitoring and advice on when to sell them.

Money managers have the fiduciary duty to choose and manage investments prudently for their clients. This fact means that they are in a better position to develop an appropriate strategy for investment in selling and buying securities to meet the goals that their clients want to

be met. The most significant reason for using money managers is the utilization of the expertise they have since they are professionally trained in the selection of appropriate investments by assessing a company's fundamental financial statements. Money managers are also a plethora of investment resources such as a large information pull and tools including interviews with company executives, research reports, data analysis, and advanced software for financial modeling. These resources enable these investment managers to make informed and superior investment decisions that one person not in the line of business cannot make. It is advisable to use money managers to take advantage of their professional resources and privileges to reduce investment risks. Their fees are also very reasonable, ranging from 5 to 10 percent of the size of the portfolio annually, reducing bias chances.

Company CEOs can also make biased decisions that are cognitive or information gathering as opposed to agents who develop unbiased forecasts about the future and use these forecasts to make decisions that best affect their image as money managers. Some investors are always very wary of giving up their investment decision-making powers to third parties due to overconfidence biases despite the essential roles these money investors play in investment growth. Some investors also view using third-party money managers as another cost incurred that will reduce investment volume. Using money managers in investing is advisable and essential as they have a 360-degree view of the market daily instead of individual investors.

Olson and Wu (2015) analyzed different risk factors for investors and posit that every investor has their principles for dealing with risks. These risk management approaches could depend on managing risks such as avoiding risks, transferring risks to insurers, reducing risks, or taking risks as they are. The risks in the security market could be contributed by natural disasters such as politics, wars, human error, malicious acts, and other natural disasters. Investors should

therefore come up with a risk management framework in which all these are to be considered, especially when coming up with a conceptual framework and approaches to reduce risks, avoid risks, transfer risks to insurers and accept risks as they are. There is an identified factor in the uniqueness of the securities market, and challenges are posed from several angles, including strict government policies and regulations that aim to unscrupulous business dealings as a risk factor in the united states securities market, recognizing that this factor is a risk factor is most vital in the United States case than in any country in the world and calls for more up-to-date stock trade risk management approaches. For example, the 9/11 terror cases and the coronavirus outbreak were unforeseen cataclysms to the stock market that cost investors huge fortunes and could have been reduced through considerable portfolio diversification.

Stock markets enhance private capital and facilitate capital market improvement. Dependable and consistent accounting information is crucial for the growth of stock markets since investors rely on adequate information to reduce risk by making informed investment decisions. Seeking up-to-date financial information has substantial effects on the volatility of the stock process. In response to this, company managers prepare accounting information to enable potential investors to make economic and investment decisions to lessen the volatility of stocks. Many companies have undergone very turbulent times in their growth, which is related to collapsing investor interests.

Several factors, along with accounting information, such as financial policy, industrial policy, expectations of investors, market supervision, foreign trade policy, and internal factors, can change the stock price. Among all the listed factors, accounting information is the most important one used by investors to base their investment choices on the company stock and reduce risk. The price of the stock of a company reflects the future profit. An investor will only

analyze the financial statements' information when evaluating the price of stocks of a company on bourse only if it furnishes them with constructive information. Due to this, financial information must hold two qualitative properties; they have to be relevant and reliable for it to be valid and acceptable to potential stakeholders. One of the most important financial reporting objectives is providing relevant information to equity investors for the estimation of the value of a company.

Contrastingly, the determination of shares in the capital markets is affected by such factors as accounting and non-accounting information. Accounting information refers to measuring and communicating economic events in business management, investment making, and observing receipt and disbursement of funds. Info starts in the ratio form, such as net assets per share, share earnings, dividend cover, share dividends, and share book value. Non-accounting information refers to information outside accounting, such as speculation, rumors, and gambling. The stock prices are based on company valuation on whether it is breaking even, and return measurement accrues to stakeholders, making their value a massive boost to existing and prospective investors in the capital markets.

References

Olson, D. L., & Wu, D. D. (2015). *Enterprise risk management* (Vol. 3). World Scientific Publishing Company.